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07068297660
Support@gamjiinstitute.org**

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EDITORIAL NOTE

It is with great pride and enthusiasm that we present the maiden edition of the *Gamji Journal of Arts and Humanities*, published by the Gamji Institute for Training and Research. This inaugural publication marks a significant milestone in our commitment to fostering academic excellence and contributing to the scholarly discourse in various fields of study.

The articles featured in this edition represent a diverse range of research topics, each offering valuable insights and advancing our understanding of critical issues. The depth and breadth of the studies reflect the dedication and scholarly rigor of the authors, and we are honored to showcase their work.

We extend our heartfelt gratitude to the authors for their invaluable contributions and to the peer reviewers for their diligent efforts in ensuring the quality and integrity of the research presented. We also express our appreciation to the editorial board and support staff whose dedication and hard work have made this publication possible.

As we embark on this scholarly journey, we invite readers to engage with the research presented in this journal, to reflect on the insights offered, and to contribute to the ongoing dialogue in their respective fields. We look forward to future editions and the continued growth of the *Gamji Journal of Arts and Humanities* as a platform for academic excellence and intellectual exchange.

Sincerely,

Prof. Aminu Ahmad
Chairman, Editorial Board
Gamji Journal of Arts and Humanities
Gamji Institute for Training and Research

ORGANISATIONAL POLITICS AND WITHDRAWAL BEHAVIORS: A STUDY OF PUBLIC UNIVERSITIES IN NIGERIA

By

Abdulrahman Alkali Gaji*, **Muhammad Inuwa****, **Aliyu Ibrahim*****

*Federal Inland Revenue Service, Nigeria.

Email: abdukali@yahoo.com tel: +2348065607317

**Department of Business Administration, Bauchi State University, Nigeria

Email: inuwadem@gmail.com +2347037099569

***Department of Business Administration, Bauchi State University, Nigeria.

Email: ibrahimaliyu93@yahoo.com tel: +2348038433614

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ABSTRACT

Universities in Nigeria are losing many of their intellectuals in academia due to withdrawal behaviors which are usually influenced by negative organisational politics. The purpose of this study is to evaluate the connection between three elements of organizational politics and withdrawal Behaviors. The social exchange theory was employed to support the model of the study. To achieve the objective of the study, data was collected via face-to-face questionnaire administration. 371 questionnaires were found useable for further analysis and Smart PLS 4 was employed in making statistical inferences. The finding from the study revealed that general political behaviours have no link with lecturers' withdrawal behaviours while employees' political inaction and reward politics have a sound link with lecturers' withdrawal behaviours. The study offers a better understanding of the extent to which organisational politics influence lecturers' withdrawal behaviours. The study recommends that universities in Nigeria establish policies that will reduce unhealthy political antics.

Keywords: Employee's political behaviours (EPB), Employees' political inaction (EPI), Reward politics (RP), Withdrawal behaviour (WB) Perception of Organisational Politics (POP)

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The effective performance of any human-made system is bound by how sound the human capital is. Withdrawal behaviour is one of the undeniable daily happenings when the work environment is bedeviled by an unfair work climate. Withdrawal behaviour (WB) occurs when people feel less committed to their assigned jobs or voluntarily leave their jobs due to certain workplace stressors. Workers can withdraw from the reality of their work environment physically or psychologically. Physical withdrawals is linked to issues of turnover, absenteeism, and deliberate delay in job accomplishment. Psychological withdrawal on the other hand, relates to emotional or mental detachment from the workplace where employees reduce their commitments, dedication and loyalty to their organisation. It is also associated with lateness to work, job anxiety, intention to quit, and lack of commitment to work responsibilities (Gaji et al., 2021; Okarche, 2020). Generally, employees usually decide to quit work when they perceive that their place in the organization is not secured (Addai et al., 2022). Withdrawal behaviour among lecturers has resulted in the loss of knowledge and expertise in universities which has direct consequences in increasing the cost of training and recruitment of new lecturers. Politics in the workplace is a primary cause of withdrawal because it creates a state of tension, uneasiness, anxiety and other adverse outcomes which often have negative consequences on employees' performances. For an organization to have employees with the right skills and expertise, the political environment in the organization must support human resource management practices such as hiring, selection, placement, promotion, rewards and staff intellectual development. Where the political environment in an organisation fails to support HR practices, employees in such workplace usually develop withdrawal behaviour (Opoku et al., 2020).

Many lecturers are physically present in the work environment but mentally absent. They are in the university community just because getting new work is hard to come by in a country like Nigeria. Job commitment among lecturers in universities is a function of adequate work conditions and a conducive work environment (Zayad & Alzubi, 2018). However, universities in Nigeria are bedeviled by an unfair working climate which promotes the selfish interest of the few (Adeniji et al., 2022). Universities all over the globe are key to solving many critical problems in all walks of life. A favourable workplace

and highly competent academicians are the bedrock for the sustainable development of any higher institution of learning. Many intellectuals in the academic environment were negatively affected by politics which can be seen from the general political behaviours of co-workers, political inaction, and reward politics (Asad et al., 2020; Rizwan et al., 2017). Numerous key activities of universities in Nigeria are politicized. Such activities include appointment into key faculty positions, membership of committees, sponsorship of research and academic conferences and course allocation (Aniefiok et al., 2020).

Despite many studies on organizational politics, there are limited studies in the context of Nigerian universities. Many of these studies focus on Western contexts, and the variables tested were not jointly observed in academic environments with a broad scope. The study of the three components of organizational politics (general political behavior of co-workers, political inaction, and reward politics) was not previously tested as a factor influencing withdrawal behavior among university lecturers in North East Nigeria. This study aligns with recommendations for further research on organizational politics. Understanding the dynamics of politics in academia will significantly improve the management of harmful workplace stressors. The main aim of the study is to evaluate whether organizational politics influences withdrawal behavior among lecturers. Specifically, the study examines the relationship between employees' political behavior, employees' political inaction, reward politics, and withdrawal behavior among university lecturers in North East Nigeria.

2.0 LITERATURE

Organizational politics refers to behaviors and actions within an organization that are self-serving and aimed at promoting personal agendas rather than organizational goals (Ferris et al., 2019). One of the frequently discussed issues in today's ever-changing work climate is office politics, which involves behaviors occurring both consciously and subconsciously among employees, managers, and chief executives (Ullah et al., 2019). Political practices in the workplace are enacted to promote self-interest, often at the expense of others and the organization itself (Cheng et al., 2020; Yin et al., 2017). Favoritism-based actions in many work climates have negatively subdued workers' psychological and physical wellbeing. Organizational politics has created a stressful environment characterized by uncertainty and obscurity in the workplace, which impedes

organizational productivity and individual employees' focus on their jobs (Clercq et al., 2022). According to progress in research, organizational politics revolves around three dimensions, as outlined by Kacmar and Ferris (1991): general political behaviour, which includes self-serving behaviours by workers and managers; 'go along to get ahead' (political inaction), which involves maintaining positive relationships with everyone in the organization to attain suitable rewards; and reward politics, which involves partial treatment in the application of pay and promotion policies within the organization.

2.1 EMPLOYEES' GENERAL POLITICAL BEHAVIOUR

Employees' general political behaviour comes in the form of workers' manipulative behaviour targeted towards promoting self-interest at the expense of the common goal of all stakeholders (Shahani et al., 2019). Workers behave politically when organisations have ambiguous goals, standards and rules. Political actions among individuals tend to prevail in such organisations (Nwizia Tordumbari Julius & Alagah, 2017; Shelton et al., 2020). An uncertain work environment provides room for the promotion of self-embedded interests that contradict the main objective of the organisation. Similarly, uncertainty hurts the decision-making process, as decisions made under unclear policies and rules have always been vulnerable to political outplay (Letshaba & Chinomona, 2019). Similarly, political antics in the workplace create different interest groups in the workforce which often results in unhealthy rivalry in the organisation. The rivalry between employees of the same organisation impairs the functionality of both the individuals and the organisation. Whenever an organization favours individuals who are self-centred, a greater number of individuals in such an organization will become less committed to the work (Khan et al., 2019). Individuals resort to political behavior when the work environment has ambiguous processes, which promote self-serving behavior. Politics distort the workflow in an organization. Employees often attempt to leave their jobs when political manipulation is perceived as a determinant of career advancement (Olufayo & Akinbo, 2022).

2.2 EMPLOYEES POLITICAL INACTION

Individuals who avoid conflicts or competition in their organizations are not viewed as hostile by those who engage in political behavior (Sheikh et al., 2020). Workers who do

not partake in political behavior are seen by politically influential groups within the organization as non-threatening and are often welcomed by such groups, receiving favorable decisions and actions for not interfering with workplace politics (Ajijala & Seun, 2019). Political inaction can be a sensible and advantageous tactic for promoting one's interests in a highly politicized office environment (Hochwarter et al., 2020; Mishra et al., 2016; Ugwu & Onyishi, 2013). Workers who are afraid to engage in office politics tend to ally with power brokers group because of their influence in deciding the faith of both the organisation and its workers (Meisler et al., 2020), but many who don't believe in workplace politics normally withdraw silently (Asad et al., 2020). People who are not actively involved in office politics always try to find their way out of such work environment by either disengaging physically or psychologically (Mishra et al., 2016).

2.3 REWARD POLITICS

Finally, organisational politics may be seen in pay and promotion policies. Many human capital management policies are planned in a manner that promotes political behaviour, even though implementers of policies normally find themselves in a mix of politics unknowingly because human resources practices are sometimes designed in a manner that gives rise to unfair practices that promote individual-centred interests against the goals of the organisation (Bwonya et al., 2020). Such practices will give rise to a culture in which influence tactics is an everyday activity of the organisation. Organizations can design reward systems that perpetuate political behaviour in a variety of ways (Aniefiok et al., 2020). For example, a reward system that is individually oriented promotes self-centred attitudes rather than the common goal of the organization (Khushk et al., 2021). However, organisations that promote politics in the work environment are encouraging unfair politics which hurts the general performance of both workers and the organisation (Stefano et al., 2019). Therefore, when politics is perceived as a factor in receiving rewards, more employees will engage in political behavior to get ahead, creating an environment that nurtures political action (Bhatti et al., 2019).

2.4 WITHDRAWAL BEHAVIOUR

Withdrawal behaviour refers to actions that cause employees to distance themselves from their organizations either physically or mentally, and such behavior can have a

detrimental effect on the entire work environment. Withdrawal behaviours are associated with impairment in productivity, dedication, commitment and turnover intention (Okache, 2020; Shapira-Lishchinsky & Even-Zohar, 2011; Tian et al., 2021). Hence, it reduces concentration in job accomplishment and drive a decline in general work performance (Mishra et al., 2020). Withdrawal attitudes are the process by which workers detach themselves from their work environment through deliberate negligence, absenteeism, lowered commitment, and eventual voluntary turnover (Burriss et al., 2008). Employees start withdrawing from their organization by reducing work effort, disassociating with office colleagues, and late accomplishment of tasks given. The first step to final withdrawal behaviour is to search for a new job (Arshad & Puteh, 2015). Similarly, withdrawal behaviour is an attitude/action which obstructs worker productivity and organizational performance When employees face hyperpolitics in their organization such workers remain silent and even refrain from reporting activities that are detrimental to their organization's goals (Beehr & Gupta, 1979).

2.5 RESEARCH FRAMEWORK AND HYPOTHESES DEVELOPMENT

The literature review reveals gaps in the findings and opinions of past studies. Whereas some views agree that politics in the workplace can influence withdrawal behaviour directly, others argue that this relationship is not conclusive and is subject to other factors. The study was conceptualized as a result of calls for further studies by Abbad et al. (2020) and Chan and James (2020). The framework of this research is presented in Figure 2.1.

Figure 2.1: Research Framework

Social Exchange Theory (SET) is fundamental in comprehending employer/employee behaviours in the work environment. This theory is among the few theories used in explaining the behaviour of individuals in a work setting (Cropanzano & Mitchell, 2005). SET is commonly used in many behavioural sciences research such as sociology and anthropology, social psychology and organisational behaviour. SET theorizes that people relate with one another based on their experience of prior interaction (Emerson, 1976). Reciprocity is a normal practice by people, reciprocating in their daily dealing with people both in society and place of work responding positively to good actions and negatively to bad actions. The theory offers an impressive submission on office politics and its consequences. When employees perceive fair and just treatment in the workplace, their attitudes toward the organization tend to be positive. Conversely, in environments plagued by toxic co-workers and ineffective management, employees often react reciprocally by reducing their efforts and commitment.

Hussain et al. (2020) reported the result of the examination of the association between employees' feelings on workplace politics and associated outcomes. The study report has shown that organisational politics is negatively linked to satisfaction on the job and workers' commitment at work. The study also found a strong bond between perception politics by workers and withdrawal behaviour and unproductive work behaviour.

Khattak et al., (2020) in their survey titled "The Impact of Political Perception in Work Environment on the Link Between Sensed Unfairness and irregular behaviours at Work", found that injustice in organisations decreases staff productivity. Injustice in organisations leads to job anxiety, work stress, intention to quit, reduced commitment and above all withdrawal behaviour.

Gupta, Singhal, & Chauhan (2021) piloted an assessment to evaluate the impact of politics on organisational affairs, worker turnover and employee performance in banks. One of the vital outcomes of this study justified that office politics was reasonably linked with withdrawal behaviour and work stress is strongly connected to employee turnover. Furthermore, Chan and James (2020) found that politics in the workplace reduces job satisfaction and increases emotional exhaustion and intention to quit.

Ahmed (2018) investigated the relationship between three antecedents of organisational politics - favouritism, reward system, and limited resources in a plan to quit. Organisational politics has a strong alliance with the intention to quit. The study found that favouritism, politics in reward and resource allocation are antecedents to organisational politics and they often lead to withdrawal behaviour. Based on the theoretical and empirical evidence, the following presumptions were established thus;

H₁: There is a positive relationship between employees' general political behaviour and withdrawal behaviour

H₂: There is a positive relationship between employees' political inaction and withdrawal behaviour

H₃: There is a positive relationship between reward politics and withdrawal behaviour

3.0 METHODS

In this study, the population is 9047 which comprises lecturers at all levels. Data was collected from 385 lecturers of 13 public universities in North East region of Nigeria and 75% of the respondents have over 10 years of working experience in the university system and have a PhD. The academic positions of the participants in this study ranged from lecturer I to professorial positions. In the data collection process, 13 research assistants were engaged and the process spanned the period of 4 weeks. The study utilized 371 of the retrieved questionnaires as basis for further statistical analysis. The study achieved a 93% response rate because the research assistants engaged in data collection are staff of the universities under study.

3.1 MEASUREMENT

The instruments for data collection in this study were measured using a five-point Likert scale ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree. The three elements of organisational politics which serve as independent variables were measured by adapting the perception of organizational politics scale from the studies of Ferris and Kacmar (1992). For example, employees' general political behavior was measured using indicators such as 'favoritism rather than merit determines who gets ahead around here.' To measure employees' political inaction, the 'go along to get ahead' scale with eight items

was used, including statements like 'agreeing with powerful people is the best alternative in this organization.' In measuring reward politics, items related to pay and promotion policies from Ferris and Kacmar (1992) were adapted, such as 'The stated pay and promotion policies have nothing to do with how pay raises and promotions are determined.' To measure withdrawal behavior, the study adopted the measurement scale of Cropanzano and Grandey (1997), including items like 'For me, this is not the best of all organizations to work with.'

4.1 DATA ANALYSIS

The data collected in this study was subjected to convergent validity via assessment indicator loadings, internal consistency reliability using Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficient and the composite reliability, convergent validity using average variance extract (AVE) and discriminant validity by employing the fornell-larker criteria and heterotrait-monotrait ratio (HTMT) principle. The Cronbach Alpha (CA), the composite reliability (CR), and the average variance extract (AVE) have made the required threshold of 0.7 for CA, 0.7 for CR and 0.5 for AVE (Hair et al., 2011) as depicted below.

Table 4.1: Convergent Validity of Measurement Model

Construct	CA	CR	AVE
Employees' Political Behaviour	0.88	0.871	0.627
Employees 'political inaction	0.804	0.897	0.553
Reward Politics	0.740	0.912	0.596
Withdrawal Behaviour	0.868	0.898	0.559

Source: Researcher's survey, 2023

4.1.2 Discriminant Validity – Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT) Criterion

The HTMT was recently introduced to the literature because of the weaknesses identified in the Fornell-larker methods of discriminant validity assessment. It was established that the Fornell-larker approach lacks the reliability to detect discriminant validity issues among constructs (Henseler et al., 2015). Studies also affirm that the Fornell-larker technique hardly identifies small differences among constructs which makes it difficult to identify discriminant validity issues (Hair et al., 2017). It is further believed that HTMT approach to discriminant validity assessment is robust and provides a better evaluation in identifying discriminant validity problems (Voorhees et al., 2016). After detecting the flaws of the Fornell-Larcker approach, Henseler et al. (2015) proposed a more robust procedure known as the Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT) for detecting discriminant validity among constructs.

Henseler et al. (2015) maintained that all the values above 0.90 display discriminant validity problems. It is also the position of Gold, Malhotra, and Segars (2001). Similarly, Kline (2011) suggests that a value that is not above 0.85 also indicates the absence of discriminant validity. However, if the constructs are conceptually similar, a higher, less conservative threshold value of 0.90. The result in Table 4.7 has shown that all the values fall within an acceptable threshold, and therefore, discriminant validity is not an issue of concern in this study.

Table 4.3: Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT)

Constructs	EPB	EPI	OC	RP	WB
EPB					
EPI	0.762				
RP	0.575	0.759	0.182		
WB	0.428	0.636	0.272	0.678	

4.1.4 STRUCTURAL MODEL ASSESSMENT MODEL

The process of structural model assessment test of the relationship between the constructs in the model involves using Beta values, assessment of the level of coefficient of determination (R^2), assessment of effect size (f^2), (Hair et al., 2017; Ringle, et al., 2019). Thus, these criteria were used for the assessment of the structural model in this study.

The primary assessment of the structural model's power of prediction is the determination of the coefficient (R^2). The coefficient of determination reveals the collective predictive power of the independent constructs (Reward politics, Employees' political behaviour, and Employees' Political Inaction) on the dependent construct (Withdrawal behaviour) in the model. The R^2 also signifies the level of variance in the dependent construct explained by all the independent constructs in the structural model (Hair et al., 2014). Figure 4:1 indicated that the entire four independent constructs in the structural model have a moderate effect on the endogenous construct with $R^2 = 0.403$. This shows that the collective effect of the independent constructs explains about 40 per cent of the variance in the endogenous construct (i.e., Withdrawal behaviour).

The effect size (f^2) tells the level of influence of an individual predicting variable on the dependent variable. It indicates the power of the independent variables in determining the variation in the dependent construct. It also displays the gap in the R^2 value due to the direct removal of the independent variable in the model. Consequently, the effect size (f^2) is applied when measuring the importance of every construct in the model. Therefore, it can be said that the higher the effect size of an independent variable in the model, the higher the link it has with the dependent variable.

In addition, many studies have identified effect size based on scales of 0.02 as small, 0.15 as medium and 0.35 as high effects respectively while any effect size of less than 0.02 is considered as no effect therefore, any construct with an effect size value of less than 0.02 is seen as construct with no influence on the dependent variable in the model (Cohen, 2012) The Table 4.9 reveal the respective effect sizes of all latent variables. It shows that employees' political behaviour with an effect size (f^2) value of 0.00 does not affect

employees' withdrawal behaviour and employees' political inaction with a small effect (f^2) value of 0.063. Similarly, reward politics ($f^2=0.125$) with moderate effect size.

Table 4.4 Effect Size (f^2)

CONSTRUCTS	WITHDRAWAL	
	BEHAVIOUR	EFFECT SIZE
EMPLOYEE'S POLITICAL BEHAVIOUR	0.000	No effect
EMPLOYEE'S POLITICAL INACTION	0.063	Small effect
REWARD POLITICS	0.125	Moderate effect

The path coefficients are the estimates of the hypothesized relationship between the endogenous construct (Withdrawal Behaviour) and the exogenous constructs (Reward Politics, Employees' Political Behaviour, Employees' Political Inaction) in the structural model. The strength of the relationship is indicated by the magnitude and significance of the estimates. The second step is to assess the significance of structural model relationships. To assess the significance of variance-based approaches, such as PLS-SEM, non-parametric bootstrap was applied. The bootstrap sample enables the estimated coefficients in PLS-SEM to be tested for their significance by computing t-values and p-values for all the structural path relationships.

Table 4.5.8 shows the path coefficients (β) with their respective t- and p-values. As shown in Table 4.5. 8, all three paths showed positive and significant (or insignificant) relationships with Withdrawal behaviour. However, the highest positive significant (or insignificant) path relationship was between Employees' political behaviour and Withdrawal behaviour ($\beta = 0.012$, $t = 0.161$, $p = 0.436$), followed by employees' Political Inaction ($\beta = 0.285$, $t = 3.858$, $p = 0.000$); then, Reward politics ($\beta = 0.349$, $t = 5.43$, $p = 0.000$). Figure 4. 3 shows the structural model indicating the path coefficients of the model of the study.

4.2 RESULTS

4.2.1 RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN EMPLOYEES' POLITICAL BEHAVIOUR AND WITHDRAWAL BEHAVIOUR

The first hypothesis (H₁) stated that “there is a significant positive relationship between employees' political behaviour and Withdrawal Behaviour.” The results of standardized regression weights from Figures 3 and 4, and Table 4.12 suggested a positive relationship between Employees' political behaviour and Withdrawal behaviour ($\beta = 0.012$, $t = 0.161$, $p = 0.436$). In other words, the regression weight for Employees' political behaviour in the prediction of Withdrawal behaviour is significantly different from zero at the p-value of 0.43. Based on the results, it can be concluded that Employees' political behaviour has an insignificant link with Withdrawal behaviour. Thus, the hypothesis (H₁) that there is a positive relationship between Employees' political behaviour and Withdrawal behaviour is rejected. The outcome of the study asserts that lecturers in universities remain active in their daily official routines even in the face general unhealthy political behaviour of their colleagues, The finding from this study corresponds with related studies by Chan and James (2020) which state that there is no link between co-workers' individual political behaviour and emotional exhaustion as well as turnover intention. Similarly, this study was also supported by the work of Nnenna & Mbah (2019) which found that there is a strong link between organizational politics and employee performance. The study was conducted among selected tertiary institutions in Anambra State, Nigeria. By implication, the study revealed that politics has a negative relationship with withdrawal behaviour among the academic staff of the tertiary institution.

In the same vein, the study demonstrates that co-lecturers who act self-centred to gain valued outcomes have no impact on the behaviour of other lecturers in the university in terms of leaving their work physically and psychologically. The position of this study was further authenticated by Ugwu & Onyishi (2013) who found a negative connection between Nigerian university lecturers' general political behaviour and work dedication. The objective of individuals who engage in office politics is to drive resourceful benefit to their favour at the detriment of others. Such behaviour can be explained through the tenet of conservation of resources theory which states that behaviours and actions among people are derived from their needs to get more useful resources and safeguarding the

resources from any loss (Bon & Shire, 2022). Therefore, employees who cannot cope with unfair political climates in their workplace usually reduce their commitment, loyalty and dedication on the job as a way of reciprocating the unjust treatment they receive.

4.2.2 RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN EMPLOYEES' POLITICAL INACTION AND WITHDRAWAL BEHAVIOUR

The second hypothesis (H₂) stated that “There is a significant positive relationship between employees’ political inaction and Withdrawal behaviour.” The results in Table 4.1 and Figure 4.1 show that the relationship between Employees’ Political Action and Withdrawal behaviour is positive and significant ($\beta = 0.285$, $t = 3.858$, $p = 0.000$). In other words, the regression weight for employees’ Political Inaction in the prediction of Withdrawal behaviour is significantly different from zero at the p-value of .000. Therefore, the hypothesis (H₂) that there is a positive relationship between Employees’ Political Inaction and Withdrawal behaviour is accepted.

The result of this study depicts that those lecturers in Nigerian universities who keep away from politics in their faculties often silently withdraw from the university either physically or psychologically. Lecturers who keep themselves away from politics in the university usually have negative feelings about political happenings and they become less committed and, in some instances, seek jobs outside the working environment. The fear of the unknown in the face of dark politics in universities made many lecturers not to take part in fruitful academic discussions which directly increases knowledge-hiding behaviour which eventually hurts knowledge advancement. The outcome of the study is consistent with related scholarly studies which found that employees' lack of action when politics is repeatedly happening in their workplace is a logical display of withdrawal from the reality of the work environment (Al-Abrow, 2018; Gan, 2020; John & Manikandan, 2019).

Lecturers' inaction translates into their disapproval of the politics in the universities hence the positive relationship between political inaction and withdrawal behaviour.

4.2.3 RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN REWARD POLITICS AND WITHDRAWAL BEHAVIOUR

The third hypothesis (H₃) states that “There is a significant connection between reward politics and withdrawal behaviour”. The results of standardized regression weights from

Figures 3 and 4, and Table 8 suggested a positive and significant relationship between reward politics and Withdrawal behaviour ($\beta = 0.349$, $t = 5.43$, $p = 0.000$). In other words, the regression weight for reward politics in the prediction of withdrawal behaviour is significantly different from zero at the p-value of 0.000. Based on the results, it can be concluded that reward politics have a positive and significant relationship with Withdrawal behaviour. Thus, the hypothesis (H_3) that there is a positive relationship between Reward politics and Withdrawal behaviour is accepted.

This study asserts that many university lecturers in northeast Nigeria have demonstrated that preferential treatment in rewards is one of the root causes of withdrawal behaviours. Consequently, lecturers in Nigerian universities are nowadays looking for jobs outside due to poor remuneration, incentives, and above all, unfair conditions of service as well as internal office politics which often undermines staff wellbeing in academic faculties.

The findings of this study align with those of Nwizia, Tordumbari, Julius, and Alagah (2017), and Murtaza et al. (2022), who investigated the effect of perceived organizational politics and effort imbalance on work outcomes. Additionally, this study concurs with Imran and Haque (2018), who found that politics played by supervisors during employee appraisals negatively impact employees' job performance as well as overall organizational outcomes.

Table 4. 5: Significance Effect of Direct Path Coefficient

Hypothesis	Relationship	Original sample (O)	Standard beta	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values	Decision
H1	EPB -> WB	0.010	0.012	0.064	0.161	0.436	Rejected
H2	EPI -> WB	0.290	0.285	0.075	3.858	0.000	Accepted
H3	RP -> WB	0.341	0.349	0.063	5.430	0.000	Accepted

Source: Extracted from SmartPLS 4 output, 2024.

5. CONCLUSION

This study was underpinned by the conservation of resources theory and was further supported by the social exchange theory. The study examined the moderating effect of organizational culture on the relationship between organizational politics and withdrawal behaviour. It is, therefore, very important to know that politics in the Nigerian university system when not adequately managed leads to withdrawal behaviour by lecturers which has detrimental effects on the goals of the highest body of learning and research.

6. RECOMMENDATION

This study recommends that University administrators should put in place strategies that will address dysfunctional political behaviour. University leaders should act like role models to induce followers to learn from them. They should create an environment where all players share the same goals. Based on the general recommendations above the following specific recommendations are made:

- i. Universities must put efforts in place to manage employees' political behaviour which undermines the efforts of others in the organisation.
- ii. University management must implement policies that identify, manage and control political actions because cordiality among employees is a key to organisational success.
- iii. Policies by universities in terms of pay raises, appointments, performance awards, job placement and scholarship/conference attendance should be done fairly.

7. IMPLICATION OF FINDINGS

Theoretically, this study has further enriched social exchange theory. This assertion was validated by the study which revealed that employees who benefit from politics in their workplace tend to continue to be active while employees who are negatively affected by politics usually become less committed and look for new jobs. The SET has laid the foundation for many studies (Chinomona, 2016) to unveil the relationships between workplace politics and other adverse outcomes demonstrated through the SET theory. The SET is a mirror that glances through studies that relate to workplace politics because

politics threatens resources in the organisation which invariably affects both human and material resources which in turn negatively influences the entire functions of the institution (Kaur & Kang, 2022).

In addition, SET offers an impressive submission on office politics and its consequences. When employees are treated fairly and justly, their thoughts toward the organization are positive. However, when an employee's work environment is bedevilled with toxic co-workers and bad managers, employees in such an environment react in a reciprocating manner by reducing their efforts and commitments. SET is among the theories that supported the study of organisational politics and related studies (Karim et al. (2021). The role of interpersonal distrust in intervening in the relationship between POP and workplace ostracism in universities.

Universities play a critical role in national development, and highly qualified lecturers are the foundation for the survival and success of any University. Universities are very much disposed to politics because people working in such institutions come from diversified backgrounds in terms of expertise, cultural orientation and professional affiliations and in such an environment, the likelihood of politics is high. The problem arising from politics has threatened the performance of many universities (Aniefiok et al., 2020; Mishra et al., 2020; Ndubuisi & Jacob, 2021; Omodan, 2019). Looking at the problem associated with politics, studying these phenomena is critical to the survival of the university system not only in Nigeria but globally. Practically the study has brought about a better understanding of political variables that affect the well-being of public university lecturers. The findings of this study offer directions and guiding principles for the establishment of policies, norms and values that promote a conducive working climate that manages politics for the betterment of all organisational stakeholders. The study gives universities a decisive understanding of organisational politics and how best to manage the phenomena. The outcome of this study is useful to all organisations both in the public and private sectors.

The outcomes of this study offer a robust footing to existing policies and decision-makers in the Nigerian university system. The universities need to introduce an effective culture to improve their existing system of administration to eliminate the toxic variable (politics). In a nutshell, employees support their organisations in an act of reciprocation

when they are made to believe that their organisations stand to support all concerned areas of their well-being. Consequently, to maintain brilliant human capital in Nigerian universities, a culture of accountability, justice, and merit should be enforced to protect the universities from the elements of organisational politics which has a real potential to deteriorate the commitments of lecturers and impede overall performance of the institution. Therefore, fair play in performance management and rewards systems in the administration of universities will make lecturers stand for the values of the institution through optimal service delivery.

8. LIMITATIONS AND SUGGESTIONS FOR FUTURE STUDIES

Although the scope of this study is wide and the result of this study brought new issues on politics in universities, it calls for further studies in the field of organisational politics because what is permanent in every organisation is change. This means that even the phenomena that cause politics and withdrawal behaviour equally change. This study focused on the negative aspects of organisational politics and withdrawal behaviour. Therefore, further studies should be conducted on the positive side of organisational politics. A comparative study shall be carried out on organisational politics and withdrawal behaviour in the public and private sectors. People often express themselves more openly in the interview process than in a closed-ended questionnaire. Therefore, this suggests that future scholars can use a qualitative approach in conducting a further test of the variables.

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